

UNDERWATER ACCELERATED AGING OF ELASTOMERIC COMPOSITE MATERIALS

A. Favre¹, E. R. Fotsing¹, Edu. Ruiz¹, M. Levesque²

¹ CREPEC, Chair on Composites of High Performance (CCHP), ² Laboratory for Multiscale Mechanics (LM2), Department of Mechanical Engineering, École Polytechnique de Montréal, Montréal, Canada

* Corresponding author (edu.ruiz@polymtl.ca)

Keywords: Glass fiber-elastomer composite, Accelerated ageing, Water immersion

1 General Introduction

Flexible composites, such as elastomer-fiber-reinforced composites, are widely used in the automotive industry for tires, timing and transmission belts. They have also recently found innovative uses in water applications, such as inflatable dams and boats or in various underwater engineering applications. For these applications, the matrix is generally a synthetic rubber and the reinforcing phase is a glass fiber fabric. Since these materials are expected to operate several years in water environment, their durability must be guaranteed. However the limited amount of data found in the literature shows that the long term behavior of such materials is still not well understood in such environment. Indeed, if the seawater ageing of thermoset composite has been widely investigated [1-4], no studies focused on elastomeric composites. Some studies examining the water ageing of elastomers show that they are usually not degraded underwater [5-7] as confirmed by the results of the investigation of AB-Malek and Stevenson [8] where a vulcanized natural rubber immersed for 42 years in sea-water showed a conservation of its physical properties. However this conclusion cannot be used for composite materials with elastomeric matrices. In fact the performance under water of this type of composite will depend not only on the elastomeric matrix but also on the fiber and more importantly on the fiber/matrix interface. Thus, if the elastomer seems to show relatively stable properties underwater, it is not always the case for the glass fibers. The presence of hydrolysable alkali oxides makes glass fibers water sensitive. Indeed the removal of these oxides at the surface of the fibers cause micro cracks which

conducts to stress concentration and loss of strength [9]. But, when fibers are used as reinforcement in the composite materials, they might be protected by the matrix. However, research works have shown that the deterioration of a composite (glass fiber/thermoset matrix) material resulted from the degradation of the glass fibers by hydrolysis [10, 11]. In the case of elastomeric composite exposed underwater, given that the mineral fiber does not absorb water contrary to elastomer matrix, it can occur a differential swelling and a development of high stress at the interface fibre-matrix. In the long term, if the adhesion is not sufficient, this stress can lead to the loss of cohesion [12]. Consequently it is essential to have a good fiber-matrix bonding in order to ensure the integrity of this material in watery condition [13]. However, given the inorganic nature of glass fibers which make the adhesion with the organic matrix difficult, fibers are usually covered with a coupling agent layer which improve interface bonding [6].

The main purpose of this study was to understand the influence of accelerated underwater ageing on the mechanical properties of elastomeric composites. An experimental procedure dedicated to these materials was developed for three elastomeric composites made from ethylene propylene diene monomer (EPDM), EPDM/silicone and polychloroprene (Neoprene) matrices and E-glass fabric.

Accelerated ageing was performed by immersing the sample in water at elevated temperature. The evolution of the properties due to the ageing by water immersion was monitored by measuring the tensile modulus, tensile strength, and the water

absorption. Furthermore scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to assess the quality of the fiber/matrix interface before and after aging.

2 Experiment details

Three sorts of elastomer matrixes namely EPDM, EPDM/silicone and Neoprene were investigated. Originally these matrixes consisted of unvulcanized sheets with a nominal thickness of 3.2 mm. The final shape of the elastomeric composite was obtained by compressing a layer of E-glass fabric between two sheets of unvulcanized rubber under high temperature. The resulting thickness of the composite materials was 4 mm. Fig.1 (a) shows a drawing of the composite materials. The design was chosen in order to protect the fabric and reduce the water infiltration. A schematic view of the final shape of the composite materials is presented in Fig.1 (b). The size of 300 mm x 140 mm (length x width) of the composite plate was determined to obtain a minimum of three samples for tensile testing. The cutting pattern is presented in Fig.1 (c) In order to obtain identical dimensions, 3 samples were cut using a die cutter and a press.

Two aging baths were set up: one bath was heated and the second one was kept at room temperature. For both baths, the water used was prepared with different salts representative of a river in province of Quebec. The heated bath contained non-renewed water maintained at 85°C. The water was not changed in order to allow a continuous ageing at constant temperature. The sampling for testing was done after 14, 47, 75, 102, 132, 222, 293 and 365 days of immersion.

The non-heated bath contained 15L of water kept at room temperature (about 21°C). Composite panels were removed from the bath and tested after 365 days of ageing. These tests were performed as a comparison basis for the accelerated testing.

In order to analyse the effect of water ageing on the composites, three characterization tests were performed. First, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to qualitatively analyse the fiber-matrix adhesion. Second, water absorption was

quantified with a gravimetric analysis according to the following formula:

$$\text{Water absorption (\%)} = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_0 is the weight of the dry specimen and W_t the weight of the wet specimen at time t .

Finally, tensile tests were performed on an MTS INSIGHT testing machine equipped with mechanical grips and a 1 kN load cell. This machine was used in order to determine the Young's modulus (E) and the ultimate strength (σ_u) of each sample.

3 Results

3.1 Interface observation

It can be seen on the SEM micrographs that the fibers were not completely impregnated, mostly due to the high viscosity of the elastomeric matrix. Consequently the adhesion was considered as peripheral since only the external row of fibers was impregnated with the matrix as presented on Fig. 2 (a). For all composites, fibers were less impregnated when moving from the edge to the middle of the tow. It was also noted that only neoprene composites possessed a weak adhesion at the interface with clearly observable debonding areas (Fig 2 (b)).

3.2 Water absorption

The percentage of water absorbed was expressed as a function of ageing time (days) at immersion temperature of 85°C. Fig. 3 shows water absorption graphs obtain for samples analyzed. It was found that the water absorption steadily increased with increasing immersion time up to a plateau. This plateau represents the maximal amount of water that the material can absorb and corresponds to the saturation level. The saturated weight gained varied from one composite material to another, around +15% for EPDM/silicone, +27% for EPDM and up to +160% for neoprene.

A direct comparison of water absorption between reinforced and unreinforced materials is shown on Fig.4. EPDM and EPDM/silicone exhibited a relatively similar amount of water absorption for reinforced and unreinforced samples (see Fig. 4 (a) and Fig. 4 (b)). However, for Neoprene, it appeared that the presence of reinforcement increased significantly the water absorption rate (see Fig. 4 (c))

3.3 Evolution of the Young's modulus after ageing

The evolution of Young's modulus after different ageing periods in water at 85°C is given in Fig. 5. Experimental data and the standard deviations are obtained from an average of 3 samples. The graphs were normalized with respect to the higher value for confidentiality purposes.

The composite made from EPDM matrix analyzed after 102 days of immersion at 85°C shows very different mechanical properties from other composites of the same material. The value of Young's modulus after 102 days of ageing is 8 times lower than the one after 132 days of immersion. This is probably related to the variability of manufacturing process or the variability of materials. For all materials the Young's modulus decrease with the increase of immersion periods exhibiting a loss of -14%, -68% and -88% of rigidity after 365 days of accelerated ageing for composites with EPDM, EPDM/silicone and Neoprene matrix respectively. Referring to Fig 5 (b) it can be seen that the impact of aging on neat rubber was less dramatic since it led to a stiffness decrease of -3% for EPDM, -49% for EPDM/silicone and -36% for Neoprene after 293 days of water immersion at 85°C. The tensile test also showed that the modulus of neat rubber was about 20 times smaller than the reinforced composites. This result was expected given the high modulus of glass fiber reinforcement.

3.4 Evolution of the failure stress after ageing

Fig. 6 shows the evolution of the failure stress of the reinforced materials after accelerated ageing at 85°C for different durations of immersion. The graphs

were normalized with respect to the higher value for confidentiality purposes.

The evolution of the failure stress is similar to the evolution of the Young's modulus. Neoprene composite which initially showed the highest failure stress value exhibits a significant decrease of its failure stress after 14 days with a loss of -80% of its initial value. EPDM/silicone which had as similar initial value of failure stress as EPDM composite shows like Neoprene a considerable drop of -70% of failure stress value after 14 days of immersion. Finally, EPDM composite shows a moderate decline of -42% after 14 days of immersion.

After 75 days of immersion, the failure stress value seems to stabilize for all materials. This behavior can be related to the fact that the equilibrium with the environment is reached, as confirmed with the water absorption graphs (Fig. 3).

After 365 days of immersion, the failure stress values of EPDM, EPDM/silicone and Neoprene materials, decreased of respectively -50%, -88% and -96% compared with unaged materials.

3.5 Interface observation after water aging

The effect of water ageing on the microstructure of the composite materials was observed by SEM. The micrographs are shown Fig. 7. It can be noticed that the interface is not identical before and after ageing (see Fig. 2). The matrix of EPDM and EPDM/silicone composites was deteriorated with the ageing as presented Fig. 7 (a) and Fig. 7 (b) where the matrix disappeared around the tow. Moreover, it can be observed that the overall aspect of the matrix has changed and became friable. The presence of porosities in the case of EPDM/silicone composites informs that components such as fillers contained inside the matrix disappear with water ageing. The case of Neoprene, Fig. 7 (c) indicates an important debonding at the interface with the presence of fibers mark in addition to a disintegration of the matrix.

4. Discussion

Reinforced elastomers are more degraded with the water ageing by comparison with neat materials. This observation confirms that elastomer components have long term durability underwater as announced by Winkelmann et al. However the rigidity of these materials is weak, about 20 times weaker than reinforced material. Thus, in various applications the reinforcement is essential. Besides, the association of the reinforcement with elastomer component create an interface which controls the mechanical properties of the composite material. Thereby a weak interface adhesion causes poor mechanical properties.

The three composite materials tested in this study exhibit very different behaviors underwater environment.

By comparing all composite plates analysed, the polychloroprene exhibits the most important rate of absorption. In the investigation of V.B. Pillai [14] he also studied the water absorption of vulcanized polychloroprene (CR) in water and reported that this material absorbed more than 200% of distilled water after 20 days at 60°C. In this study, the unreinforced Neoprene composite absorbed 16% of water after 30 days of immersion; this difference can be attributed to various parameters such as the rubber composition, the degree of vulcanization, the water composition (salt vs. distilled) [15]. According to V.B Pillai and A.N Gent this high amount of water absorbed can be explained by the presence of zinc and magnesium oxides found in curing system.

In addition, in the case of composite materials, the important gain can also be caused by structural parameters such as the presence of micro spaces or a poor interface adhesion. In order to validate this hypothesis, visual observations were performed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and micrograph of the fiber/matrix interface (Fig. 2). As expected, N_R micrograph (Fig.2 (c)) shows non uniform wetting of the fibers and voids for unaged materials. In fact the stiffness of Neoprene composite collapses after 14 days of immersion at 85°C reaching a loss of -85% of the Young's modulus value after 293 days. Obviously, the high

absorption level has a huge impact on the mechanical properties. This observation implies that the fiber/matrix is so damaged by water that glass fibers do not any more contribute to mechanical properties of the composites. The drastic decline of the ultimate stress with increasing aging time plus the micrograph of the interface after 293 days of ageing tends to confirm this hypothesis. The EPDM/silicone composite, which absorbed a lower extent of water, shows a loss of -61% of its initial stiffness (unaged material) and -84% of its initial strength after 133 days of immersion. Comparatively the unreinforced material shows a loss of -43% of its initial stiffness suggesting the deterioration of the matrix and by extension the fibre-matrix interface. The damaged state of interface observed after 293 days of ageing (Fig 7 (b)) support this assumption.

In fact, although the same process of manufacturing was used for all materials, the analysis of interface reveals different state of adhesion showing thus that EPDM composite have a better interface bonding. This can be due either to the manufacturing process (appropriate temperature and compaction pressure) or to good fiber-matrix compatibility. Given that the glass fabrics are generally treated with a sizing to improve fibre-matrix adhesion, the sizing may have a better reactivity with this matrix.

This last observation let assume that these materials will have a better ageing behavior. The ageing results of EPDM composite confirm this hypothesis, thus after 14 days of immersing its mechanical properties show a relatively slight decrease compared with EPDM/silicone and Neoprene composite. Thus, despite the amount of water absorbed, the interface is enough resistant to ensure the load transfer between the matrix and the fibers. It is finally after 293 days of immersion that EPDM composite starts to exhibit a decrease of its ultimate strength with a loss of -68%.

After 365 days of aging at room temperature, there was no significant variation in Young's modulus for all composites confirming that the fibre-matrix interface was not damaged after one year of immersion. The same observation was done for neat elastomer where only Neoprene matrix exhibited -3% loss of stiffness. Given that the room

temperature aging is characterized by slow degradation kinetics it was expected that few changes would be observed. However a decrease of failure stress (-13% and -44% for EPDM/silicone and Neoprene composites, respectively) was observed. This decline could be attributed to the aging of the fibers or the matrix probably due to water interaction.

Finally, this analysis showed that the neoprene is not appropriated for underwater application because of the high rate of water absorption and the interface degradation.

5. Conclusions

The effect of water ageing on 3 composites (E-Glass fiber / elastomer matrix) has been investigated in this paper. With the aim of finding and appropriate material for underwater application, the deterioration has been analysed in order to highlight the main physical and mechanical consequences of an accelerated ageing, which were not found in the literature. Microscopic analysis and water absorption tests correlated with the mechanical properties of composites led to a better understanding of the phenomenon which takes place underwater. In fact there are two crucial parameters to take in consideration in order to ensure long term integrity of the composite material underwater namely the fiber-matrix interface and the interaction between the matrix and its environment. The interface fiber-matrix plays an important role in mechanical strengths and weakness of composites. Consequently a strong bonding at the interface ensures load transfer and improved mechanical performances. Conversely a weak bonding leads to a sliding at the interface and the mechanical properties. Thus, as confirm by tensile results and SEM micrographs after immersion in water, a composite material with a strong interface bonding will maintain its mechanical properties over longer period of time. In order to guarantee a good interface bonding it is necessary to consider the compatibility between the

sizing of the reinforcement and the matrix used. A preliminary approach is to observe qualitatively the fiber-matrix interface with SEM.

For the interaction between matrix and its environment it was observed in this study that the behaviour underwater of elastomer vary from one material to another with the Neoprene absorbing more than +150% of water versus +15% for the EPDM/silicone. Thus it is preferable to select a matrix which absorbs a low amount of water to limit the differential swelling at fiber/matrix interface.

The contributions of this study are as follows:

1. The development of a relevant accelerated ageing method to simulate the elastomeric composite degradation underwater.
2. The setting up of a method of characterization of these materials
3. The access of data about water accelerated ageing on elastomeric composites

Fig. 1: Design of the composite material plates. (a) 3D drawing of composite materials manufactured. (b) Schematic view of the shape of composite plate for ageing test with isolated edges. (c) Schema of the 3 reinforced specimens obtained after the cut.

Fig. 2 : SEM micrograph showing the fiber-matrix interface for (a) unaged Neoprene composite on the scale of 1µm and (b) 10µm and (c) EPDM composite.

(a)

(a)

(b)

(b)

Fig. 3 : Water absorption after immersion in water at 85°C for EPDM and EPDM/silicone (a) and for Neoprene (b).

(c)

Fig. 4 : Evolution of water absorption after immersion in water at 85°C. Results obtained for the samples of (a) EPDM composite and neat EPDM, (b) EPDM/silicone composite and neat EPDM/silicone and (c) Neoprene composite and neat Neoprene.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5 : Influence of ageing in water at 85°C on the Young's Modulus. (a) Results obtained for the samples of composite materials. (b) Results obtained for the samples of unreinforced materials.

Fig. 6 : Influence of ageing in water at 85°C on Failure stress of different composites respectively EPDM, EPDM/silicone and neoprene.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 7 : SEM micrographs showing the fiber-matrix interface for aged composite after 293 days (a) EPDM (b) EPDM/silicone (c) Neoprene.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to Alstom and Hydro Quebec for supporting this project and the financial contribution of CREFARRE and Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC).

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